

Nanoscale Copper alloys powder elaborated by an amorphous citrate method: an application for the elaboration of Cu alloy/C MMC

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Summary

Amorphous citrate method is used to elaborate nanometric Copper alloy powder. This powder is then mixed with Carbon fibers and hot pressed in order to obtain dense composite material for thermo-mechanical applications. Annealing treatments are performed to create a strong carbide interfacial zone between matrix and reinforcement and therefore improve property transfer.

Keywords: Citrate method, Metal matrix composites, Carbon fiber, Copper alloys, Thermal conductivity, Coefficient of thermal expansion

Size, shape, chemical composition are the main properties of metallic powders that have to be controlled in order to optimize the final properties of materials elaborated with powder metallurgy method. Different methods such as atomization, salt decomposition, electroless or super-critical fluid processes are already used.

A chemical method is proposed to elaborate copper alloys with sub-micronic size and controlled composition: i.e. the amorphous citrate method (Figure 1). An homogeneous atomic dispersion of Copper and alloying element and proper annealing treatment lead to Copper alloy powder with nanometric grain (Figure 2) and control alloying composition.

Figure 2: Micrography of CuCr powder synthesis by amorphous citrate method.

Figure 2: Operating mode of CuCr powder synthesis by amorphous citrate method.

These Cu alloy powders are mixed with carbon fibers and then hot pressed to obtain dense materials. Annealing treatments are optimized to achieve strong carbide interfaces. Thermal conductivity and coefficient of thermal expansion are measured. Composites materials are also analyzed by Transmission Electron Microscopy, Scanning Electron Microscopy, Auger Electron Spectroscopy and X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy techniques.

Conclusion

We have used an amorphous citrate method to elaborate Copper alloy powder with nanometric grains. The powder was mixed with Carbon fibres, densified and heat treated in order to obtain composites material with controlled composition and optimized thermal properties.